

Comparative Analysis of E-Recruitment Challenges and Effectiveness in FPSC and SPSC

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Abstract

this study mainly focuses on the E-recruitment process, including its challenges following effectiveness. The two most famous public service commissions are FPSC and SPSC, this study compares both of these organizations and brings forward the conclusion.

Keywords—E-recruitment, FPSC, SPSC, Challenges, Effectiveness, Comparison.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recruitment has become an important process in the selection of the right candidates for the employer and latest trend which signifies the organizations' demands for seeking employees through latest technological methods by small and medium organizations. Also, the job sites' cost-effectiveness, speed, providing customized solutions are the main success factors of E-recruitment which provide value-added services and helping to establish a relationship with HR managers and facilitates the brand building of the companies. However, first, candidates who are seeking job opportunities have several benefits and second, certain challenges are also associated with e-recruitment processes such as internet resources.

Several organizations face various challenges in the process of recruitment and one of the main objectives of an organization is to recruit the best workforce from a large pool of applicants. Also, the prospect of a successful organization does not only depend on the financial return but also depends on how the organization develops its' human capital. Hence, internet service used in the whole procedure of e-recruitment process is a cost-effective method and easily accessed by each individual who seeks to visit jobs and other information at organization's job portal. E-recruitment also provides the facility to search for specific competencies of candidates. Organizations use two sites for recruitment one is job portals and the other one is the organization's websites. There have been several advantages and disadvantages in the e-recruitment processes. Most organizations have advantages of online recruitment method like less paperwork, streamline work process, centralized workplace, etc. on the other hand disadvantages like poor internet services in rural areas where the connection in rural side, communication gap, validity of the resume, etc. is common (Priya Unadkat, 2012).

In the light of above, the variables that are considered in online recruitment process includes the fastest mode, large pool of candidates, reducing workload, reducing turnover, attracting passive job seeker, increasing organizational performance cost, time, accessibility, specified requirements, and to assess the improvement of each stage of the recruitment process, the test variables that are considered include screening, interviewing, assessment, selection, and induction.

To search, recruit and select talented people in a specific market is a difficult task for the organization nowadays. Conversely to apply for a particular job is most difficult for educated people, who are seeking the job. Hence, there are indispensable challenges for both recruitment organizations and unemployed people who are searching for a job. Therefore to assess and examine the effectiveness of available organizations and challenges relating to both organizational efficiency and ease of people who face such challenges are very much necessary. Moreover, comparing this research can determine the effective method of E-recruitment that can be more helpful for candidates.

This study aims to assess the E-Recruitment process and its effectiveness of online recruitment to recruiters of Federal Public Service Commission (FPSC) and Sindh Public Service Commission (SPSC) public service commissions. It could be analyzed by following three objectives and those are:

1. To identify the challenges in online application processes for the job seeker.
2. To examine the effectiveness of the E-Recruitment process of FPSC and SPSC in the view of applicants.
3. To compare the E-recruitment process in FPSC and SPSC Public Service Commission.

To conclude the acceptable way of E-recruitment process in the public sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Nowadays, e-recruitment is playing an important role in the hiring process. The big companies in Pakistan have also emphasized e-recruitment after technological innovation in Pakistan (Ahmed, Tahir, & Warsi, 2015). "Many" work boards "run in Pakistan, such as job.com, Rozee. pk, Mustakbil.com, and some other social media such as LinkedIn. These work boards spread awareness to the job seeker about the job. This is therefore the right time to examine whether e-recruitment initiatives have any effect on balancing HR in a comparatively less developed country like Pakistan (Malik & Mujataba, 2018).

The study identified factors that influence the decision to recruit employees through online recruiting organizations. Cost-effectiveness and a higher response rate have an impact on online recruitment by businesses. (Islam, 2016) concluded that online recruitment productivity relies on efficiency, reliability, protection, and cost-effectiveness. The Internet, however, reaches people in single regional or national newspapers from large geographical and social contexts over advertisements, this also guarantees the possibility of better notifying job seekers about the job description. In addition to this, online recruiting and selection are the most popular internet applications in HRM operations. The targeted users can therefore be effectively attracted by online advertisements with interactive as well as rich multimedia content.

The number of job seekers using online recruitment strategy is continuously rising in line with this trend, irrespective of the increasing emphasis on OR in the social sciences and at the practical level, (Petre, Osoian, & Zaharie, 2016) research on this subject in the field of personnel selection remains limited (Roulin & Bangerter, 2013) and online recruitment platforms (or job portals) and social networking websites are experiencing significant growth. Although OR is still a relatively new process, the movement towards internet-based recruitment is visible and growing (Ouiridi, Pais, Segers, & Ouiridi, 2016).

Organizations are becoming more online-dependent at present when coping with the practices of human resource management. Today businesses prefer online-recruitment media to attract and select the best suit from a pool of possible candidates. Some benefits are guaranteed and some challenges are encountered too much by organizations relying on online recruitment (Sultana & Sultana, 2018).

The research (Khanam, Uddin, & Mahfuz, 2015) adopted the UTAUT model to assess the adoption factors and responses of university students to e-recruitment in Bangladesh. A total of 288 applicants were asked to report their response on four independent variables: success expectation, effort expectation, social impact and self-efficiency influencing user adoption or e-recruitment system acceptance, where social impact in this model was not considered to be a significant predictor.

The e-recruitment basics are monitoring: helpful in monitoring the candidate's status concerning the jobs he/she has applied for. Employer's Website: Offers work openings and knowledge collection descriptions for the same. Job portals: These bear job ads from employers and agencies, such as CareerAge, Indeed, Beast, Naukri, time jobs, etc. Online Testing: Internet assessment of applicants based on different work profiles to assess them on different criteria. Social networking: Websites such as Google+, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. help to create powerful networks and find job opportunities (Anand & Devi, 2016).

The latest trend in recruitment practices and highlights the recent trend in online recruitment practices, and we can also get ideas about how organizations can benefit from online recruitment. This paper highlighted recruitment advantages such as cost effectiveness, time saving, greater scope and wider option, The usual way to find a nominee, less paper usage and some of the disadvantages such as computer technology, large

applicants and option are also discussed and candidates are not extreme. This article concludes that conventional methods of recruiting should be replaced by e-recruitment. Combining e-recruitment with conventional approaches would speed up the recruitment process. (Hada & Gairola, 2015).

A benefit of Social Networking Sites (SNS) is that they offer an incentive for the recruiter to attract and approach 'Passive' applicants. Like active job seekers, passive applicants build and maintain a professional profile as they believe that this will get them closer to the recruiter even if they are not actively searching for a job (Nikolaou, 2014).

III. CHALLENGES OF E-RECRUITMENT

E-Recruitment has been successful since its inception, but in the direction of success, it has encountered significant challenges and obstacles. Some may not have accurate online data because they are not computer savvy. They appear to make errors such as wrongly filling their name, filling their native location, their qualifications, etc. Online resumes are quickly duplicated and are often likely to ignore the actual candidate because of duplicate increases. As resumes are submitted electronically, the validity and correctness of the details given by workers are not guaranteed. The consistency and the number of candidates through the web tools are some challenges. Several organizations have reported receiving significant numbers of applications from unskilled individuals. Candidates may not be able to search any portal or website in the absence of an Internet connection. E-Recruitment allows companies to be prepared with qualified workers and is thus connected to many corporate HR activities. E-Recruitment has proven to be an important part of the strategy for recruitment. It can be used, often by larger organizations, to keep track and manage candidate applications. In terms of cost and effectiveness, E-Recruitment has given some remarkable advantages (Anand & Devi, 2016).

A. Information of respondents

To identify the challenges in the online application process for the job seekers results indicates that there is 62.3% male and 37.7% female applicants' response to the required information. In addition to that, 65.3% are of 20 to 30 years of age and 26.4% are of 31 to 40 and also 5% above 40, and 3.3% under 19 of age are applying for jobs through the SPSC and FPSC. Among these age groups and gender groups, 38.5% are already employed in some other organizations but seeking more opportunities. Moreover, 30.3% are still a student but applying for a job and 29.5% are unemployed and looking for a job. Although others 1.7% are business owners but are in the same cue. In terms of native domicile and location of applicants, results show that 78% are from rural areas and 22% are from the urban side.

Besides that, the duration has also been discussed for which the responses indicated that less than one year is the 45.5% and 2 to 3 years 28.2% is of applying practices of applicants and also more than 5 years of duration is of 17.3% of responses and 9.1% shows 4 to 5 years.

Fig. 1. Represents duration of a job hunt

Whereas, respondents were asked about recruitment sources in which (77.7%) respondents selected on the option of internet, (46.3%) responses of Social media applications, (33.9%) responses are selected Newspaper and (7.4%) have chosen Recruitment agencies.

Fig. 2. Represents recruitment sources. Further respondents were asked why they are not in favor of E-recruitment, (49.1%) responded ‘Lack of human contact’ (40.9%) thought that is ‘discrimination against non-internet users and (30%) said there is ‘Transparency of data’.

Fig. 3. Represents reasons for not being in favor of E-recruitment

And also included disadvantages of E-recruitment 46.4% says E-recruitment ‘Limits the application audience as the internet is not the first choice for all job seekers’, 37.5% says ‘E-recruitment disappoints candidates, particularly if the website is badly designed or technical difficulties’, 25.9% have said E-recruitment make the process impersonal, which may be off-putting for some candidates, 8.9% views that ‘E-recruitment impacts on the cultural fit dimension of recruitment’ and 0.9% have ‘Technical issues’.

Fig. 4. Represents disadvantages of E-recruitment

In figure 4. Most of the respondent complaint about the access of bank branches because only selected branches of National Bank of Pakistan has given opportunities to submit with. It is too difficult to approach far away branches on time and submit an application. Secondly, printing challan is also become a difficult process for candidates, because everyone has no printer and no access to print challan form from shops or offices. The third and foremost difficult part is ID and Password recovery which is mostly faced by candidates due to old contact information they cannot apply for any current advertised post. For that candidate who is of any city have to go to head office at Hyderabad or Karachi.

Fig. 5. Represents difficulty using SPSC

However, In FPSC almost similar responses and results were received. But their candidate has not to create an account. Candidates can apply directly without making any profile or login ID / Account. There is also a leading issue is the bank branch of the National Bank of Pakistan is not in access and the candidate has to go physically to the bank for paying the challan.

Fig. 6. Represents difficulty using FPSC

IV. THE USEFULNESS OF E-RECRUITMENT

Traditional recruitment methods can be overcome by online recruitment or E-recruitment for easy access of candidates. High caliber staff is fundamental to be a successful organization and for maintaining the position of recruiting. It can lead to frustration in not finding the right person. Employers can find qualified candidates from all over the world and they are not limited to attract candidates only from their native place. The same holds for job seekers. Nevertheless of geographical location candidates can search and apply for jobs where their skills are met. Advertisement for attracting candidates and appealing to the maximum audience has become cheaper because of widespread use of the internet these days.

To check the performance of organizations in figure 7 respondents have been asking some indicative questions to examine the satisfaction role of the organization in which 34.7% shows their satisfaction and 23.7% partially satisfied, 17.8% show their dissatisfaction and 14.4% are extremely satisfied with the process and last 9.3% discouraged by the system.

Fig. 7. Represents E-recruitment satisfaction

For measuring the indicator of reliability in the below figure. 8, 87.1% of candidates show they're concerned and considered the E-recruitment system as a reliable source than other recruiting sources.

Fig. 8. Represents effectiveness of E-recruitment

Figure 9 indicates the cost-effective variable for a candidate in which 46.4% of responses believe that online recruitment is quick and 45.5% respondent that it is a cost-effective source of recruitment. Hence, no hard copy is required, no courier cost, and also save the time and physical and mental cost.

Fig. 9. Represents advantages of E-recruitment through internet

V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

After a rigorous study and survey from hundreds of people, a comparative analysis table has been made, merging all the data and responses of respondents.

A. FPSC

The Federal Public Service Commission (FPSC) is an organization of the federal government of Pakistan. It aims to provide recruitment services in government departments and after scrutiny of the whole recruitment process, it forwarded recommendations regarding appointment to the relevant authorities.

B. SPSC

The Sindh Public Service Commission (SPSC) is a provincial agency of the Government of Sindh. SPSC is responsible for recruiting bureaucrats and civil servants in various departments of the Government of Sindh. It aims to provide recruitment services in the government of Sindh for appointment purposes.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FPSC AND SPSC

S. No.	STANDARDS	FPSC	SPSC	REMARKS OF CANDIDATES
1	LOGIN/ CREATE ACCOUNT	No	YES	RESPONDENTS SAY 'YES' TO CREATE A LOG-IN ACCOUNT IS A CONVENIENT OPTION, AND 22.7% SAY 'NO' IT IS NOT CONVENIENT. AND 29.5% HAVE DIFFICULTY IN RECOVERING THE FORGOTTEN PASSWORD OF A LOG-IN ACCOUNT.
2	DIRECT FORM FILL	YES	NO	IN FPSC, CANDIDATES CAN FILL THE FORM DIRECTLY WITHOUT CREATING A LOG-IN ACCOUNT. ACCORDING TO THIS SURVEY, 48.7% OF RESPONDENTS SAY 'YES' DIRECT FILLING OF THE FORM IS A RELIABLE OPTION THAN TO CREATE A LOG-IN ACCOUNT. 47.4% SAY 'NO' IT IS NOT A CONVENIENT OPTION, REMAINING 3.9% HAVE SHARED THEIR DIFFERENT VIEWS
3	DOWNLOAD/ PRINT CHALLAN FORM	YES	YES	CANDIDATES ARE FACING TROUBLE IN PRINTING THE CHALLAN FORM. BECAUSE EVERY CANDIDATE HAS NOT THE AVAILABILITY OF A PRINTER AT HOME AND THEY HAVE TO GO TO PHOTOCOPIER SHOP FOR GETTING PRINTED CHALLAN FORM.
4	CHALLAN IS TO BE PAID IN SELECTED BRANCHES OF THE NATIONAL BANK OF PAKISTAN AND STATE BANK OF PAKISTAN.	YES	YES	IN BOTH ORGANIZATIONS, CANDIDATES HAVE TO GO FOR PAYING CHALLAN TO THE SELECTED BRANCHES OF NATIONAL BANK OF PAKISTAN AND STATE BANK OF PAKISTAN. CANDIDATES ARE FACING DIFFICULTY IN PAYING CHALLAN AT BANK BECAUSE SELECTED BRANCHES OF NBP & SBP ARE NOT IN THEIR EASY ACCESS.

VI. CONCLUSION

Most of the respondents show their interest in using internet as a recruitment source for applying and finding the jobs, the problem that they have indicated is lack of human contact and discrimination against non-internet users.

The figure 9 shows de-merits of E-recruitment and higher ratio of responses were i.e. limits the application audience as the internet is not the first choice for all job seekers.

Fig 8 shows de-merits of E-recruitment

Similar results were shown in both Public sector organizations for that respondents highlighted the problems and majority of respondent's complaint about the access of bank branches, because only selected branches of National Bank of Pakistan (NBP) and State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) provide access to submit their challan. And it is too difficult to approach timely to submit application as the Bank branches are far away. Printing of challan form is also a difficult task for candidates because every candidate has no facility of printer at home. Focusing on the rural areas, it is too costly for candidates those have to go to nearby city first to print the copy of challan and getting printed hard copy from the photocopier and then go to branch of bank for paying challan and finally fill the online application form. Hence, this process would be an obstacle for applicant to apply online. As shown in figure 9.

Fig. 9 showing problems faced by candidates in FPSC.

In SPSC, candidates are facing difficulty to recover forgotten Password of log-in account because earlier contact information (i.e email, cell number) is uploaded on the SPSC login account which is not in use by candidates at applying time. If candidate has forgotten his/her contact information i.e. email Id or mobile phone number, which was provided earlier at that point they have to faces difficulty in recovery of password.

After the analysis this can be concluded that the online bank account should be provided on website so that the candidate can pay through any mobile bank account application /easypesa account /upesa account /mobicash account and/or funds transfer from any other resources.

The Process should be easy in such a way that candidate can quickly pay the challan from any location without any difficulty. For making this in practice, it would be feasible for candidates to submit application timely and less costly and set aside mental / physical fating / bothering.

Further, a focal person and helpline number may be provided for candidates who have problem in creating / to register new login account and also recover forgotten password. Focal person must be available in every office in all cities where there offices are existing. Moreover, it is suggested that in SPSC both options may be included i.e. making profile and create login account, and directly apply without making login account. Hence, in this way a candidate who has forgotten his/her login account password and facing trouble in

recovering password can apply within due date of application submission. If the closing date is about to finish, then he/she may submit his/her application form directly without login account. Subsequently, organization may facilitate candidate for only one time to apply on due time and send message (SMS / email) him/her through official confirmation message of application submitted, to add a suggestion “you are requested to recover your login account password on earlier bases.”

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